

Assessment of Modalities of Communication in Teaching by Students of Pedagogical Specialties in Contact and Distance Learning

**Оцінка окремих аспектів спілкування викладача
зі студентами педагогічних спеціальностей
у ході контактного та віддаленого навчання**

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. *The relevance of the topic is determined by the practice of distant learning and the need to improve approaches to the organization and content of classes with students of pedagogical specialties. The problems of education with the use of information technologies have been developed for a long time, but earlier they concerned additional and other types of education, where students in general had professional skills. In this study, we are talking about students who are just starting*

their studies and when the quality of pedagogical communication affects not only the assimilation of educational material, but also forms the skills and style of activity in the pedagogical process of the students themselves. Since part of the classes took place in a contact mode, it was important to find out how students evaluate classes in different formats, in particular, the structure of communication and the skills necessary for independent work.

Goal. The aim of the study is to compare and evaluate certain aspects of communication in intramural and distance learning.

Methods of the Research. The research methods were a survey and questioning of 116 and 84 first-year students of pedagogical specialties of the University of Latvia in 2020–2021.

The Results. At the first stage, based on the survey, the criteria for successful pedagogical communication between the teacher and students in the learning process were determined. At the second stage, a survey of students was carried out in order to assess the professional qualities of a teacher and a student, which determine the optimal pedagogical communication.

Conclusions. The results obtained showed a high level of assessments of the teacher's professional qualities and satisfaction with the level of pedagogical communication by the students themselves, as well as a minimal difference in assessments in contact and remote classes. This means that the nature of communication is the same and includes respect for students, a friendly attitude towards them, passion for work, respect for the autonomy of each other and exactingness, which allows everyone to develop intellectually, master professional skills and individual teaching tools, taking into account the individual qualities of children.

Key words: pedagogical communication, structure of pedagogical communication, teacher's professional skills.

Introduction

The problem of communication is one of the most studied in psychology. Like every complex psychological phenomenon considered as a whole, communication has many aspects, each of which is important for understanding this phenomenon. Within the framework of the activity approach in psychology with the use and development of the scientific apparatus, many conceptual schemes for the analysis of activity were proposed, which made it possible to single out the components of actions: motives, goals, tasks, methods of implementation and conditions for the implementation of communication activities (Great Psychological Dictionary, 2008).

It was from the standpoint of the activity approach that the concept and structure of pedagogical communication were developed: the foundations of the ascertaining characteristics of the pedagogical process (what exactly happens in the process of communication), the system of interactions between the teacher and the student, the purpose of the activity, the subject of interaction between the participants in the activity, the communication, etc. (Shakirov, 2009). The specified author considers pedagogical communication to be a contextual interpersonal interaction of two subjects of activity – a teacher and a student, and the objects of interaction are the psychological qualities of the personality of the participants in the process.

P. Aleksandrovich also believes that a significant part of pedagogical difficulties is due not so much to a lack of scientific, methodological training of teachers, but to a deformation of the environment of professional and pedagogical communication (Aleksandrovich, 2012). Some authors classify pedagogical communication at the university as a much more effective type of communication, because in specialized subjects, both the teacher and the student are colleagues, therefore, the level of mutual understanding is easier to achieve. Although the personal qualities of a teacher and a student have been studied in detail, not all issues have been resolved.

I. Guzhva (2011) emphasizes that in pedagogical psychology and pedagogy, the teacher is considered in connection with the study of his/her professional abilities, the characteristics of pedagogical activity, pedagogical communication, professionally significant personality traits, as well as the perception and understanding of the teacher's personality by schoolchildren and students. However, it is not clear to what extent the qualities of the teacher's personality contribute to the professional growth of the student (ibid.). The classic work of Kan-Kalik (1987), noted that pupils of senior, and especially graduation class cease to value the personal qualities of the teacher so highly, because in the first place is the teacher's exactingness and the level of knowledge achieved in his classes, albeit not so emotionally comfortable.

The problem of this study was determined by the transition of the majority of students to distant learning. For both the teacher and the students, the conditions of interaction have changed, while the goals and objectives of communication have remained the same.

The *object of the research* is professional communication between a teacher and students at contact and distant lectures.

The *subject of the research* is the assessment of certain aspects of communication with the teacher by students of pedagogical specialties in contact and distance learning.

The *questions* that were supposed to be answered at the end of the study were as follows:

Q1: Are the differences in the form of teaching fundamental for students' perception of the nature of communication with the teacher?

Q2: How to optimally organize communication so that the goals and objectives of the pedagogical process are achieved?

Methodology of the Research

The study involved first-year students of pedagogical specialties of LU. At the first stage of the study, students assessed the personality traits of the teacher, contributing to their mastery of the educational material. The survey was carried out both orally and in writing. The assessment of the criteria for successful teaching activity was carried out in a comprehensive manner, sometimes descriptively, since the statements of the students were both a live conversation and in the form of written assignments. The statements at this stage were not specific to a specific lecturer. Subsequently, students ranked the features of the teacher's professional communication. The study involved 116 students, who studied half of the course (4 lessons) by contact, and the other (4 lessons) – remotely. At the end of the course, students identified and assessed their qualities that they acquired in the course of classes. As a result of the analysis of the answers, a questionnaire was drawn up.

The quality of the teacher's pedagogical communication was proposed to be assessed from 1 to 10 points according to the following criteria: respect of the teacher for the student's personality, enthusiasm for joint creative activities, friendly attitude towards students, distancing from the subject of communication and the threat of punishment for academic failure. The latter criterion appeared due to the fact that many people noted the requirements for the level of knowledge at the end of the course as very high, and the conditions for obtaining a positive assessment are vague and frightening.

The second part of the questions related to the mastery of the peculiarities of pedagogical communication by the students themselves. It included honesty, education and a high intellectual level, professionalism in pedagogical communication, the student's ability to recognize the individual characteristics of a child.

At the next stage, a survey of students was carried out. This time the respondents were the students of the first year with a mixed type of classes, who were taught by different teachers. 82 students answered the questions. The questionnaire had two options: the peculiarities of the teacher's pedagogical communication and the acquisition of professional skills by the student in the process of contact and distant studies. Subsequently, the mean for each assessment criterion was determined and the specificity of the assessment of contact and distant classes was compared.

Results

The results obtained were to some extent unexpected, since the average marks according to the criteria of professional pedagogical communication turned out to be high and close both in contact and non-contact forms of education.

Table 1

Average Marks According to the Criteria of Pedagogical Communication Given by Students

	Distance learning	Contact learning
Respect for the student's personality	9.06	9.27
Passion for joint creative performance	9.06	9.06
Friendly attitude towards students	9.43	9.2
Distancing from students	5.9	5.97
Intimidation with punishment	1.96	5.98
Honesty	8.95	8.85
Intellectual skills	8.76	9.02
Professional skills	8.99	8.99
Ability to interest children	8.8	8.83
Understanding the personal make up of children	8.8	8.81

An obvious disadvantage of the rating scale was the absence of a zero grade, since many respondents believed that the teacher did not

intimidate them with a difficult exam or any sanctions in case of a bad answer at the exam. Therefore, it can be assumed that according to this criterion, the marks would be different. Next, we will analyze the results obtained. Attention is also drawn to the fact that with a distant form of communication, the fear of punishment from the teacher has significantly decreased. We explain this by the fact that in remote learning, general requirements for mastering the subject were proposed in the form of exercises and independent tasks performed during the seminar. This probably helped to understand the direction of independent work to a greater extent than in contact classes, where the intensity of independent work was much less.

Fig. 1

Features of Pedagogical Communication in Contact and Distant Classes

Discussion

As we have already mentioned, the scores turned out to be high and only slightly different for contact and remote forms of work. In our opinion, this means that the nature of communication is the same in all forms of communication: subject-subject interaction of people. Probably, such representations were facilitated by the establishment of live contact

at the beginning of classes. Pandemic-related restrictions appeared in the middle of the course.

In terms of the level of assessments, the criterion “intimidation”, which has already been mentioned, and “distancing” differ. At the first stage of the study, when determining the assessment criteria, many respondents noted the distancing of the teacher and students. Perhaps they meant being far from each other in a geographical sense. However, during the assessment process, it was found that most of the students perceive the criterion of “distancing” in a negative connotation, as the teacher’s indifference towards the audience.

Having studied the issue, it was possible to find out that there is a study where distancing in the context of pedagogical communication is considered as a prerequisite for non-interference in the psychological space of another person, subtlety in handling, taking into account the position of another. Duchnovskij (2013) the author, having studied the interpersonal relations of the subjects of the educational process, believes that the harmony and disharmony of interpersonal relations are associated with a change in the socio-psychological distance in relationships, the rejection of any manipulative control and the desire for superiority over a partner, and the socio-psychological distance is regulated by external (environmental) factors, personal characteristics of subjects, as well as their activity.

Thus, without explaining the meaning of the criterion to the research participants, we received incorrect results.

The idea of studying the qualities of a university teacher separately as a person and as a professional belongs to Guzhva (2011). She and her co-authors have created a diagnostic questionnaire “Teacher through the eyes of students” (Guzhva & Pobokin, 2020). The features of the teacher as a person and a professional are considered very broadly, the list of qualities is very voluminous, however, in our research we were interested in the differences in the assessment of the two forms of communication and what students who are starting to learn noted as important for themselves in this communication. In the future, it is possible to adapt I. Guzhva’s questionnaire for our audience.

Returning to the characteristics of the respondents, it should be noted that approximately 2/3 of all students work as teachers in school and kindergarten, their age is from 18 to 56 years old, therefore, they understand the specifics of communication. It would be important to

check how younger students perceive the distant form of education. However, their number was insufficient for processing.

Conclusions

(1). In the process of the study, for most of the indicators of pedagogical communication between the teacher and students, the assessments for both contact and distance learning were high and differed very slightly. The scores for distancing and bullying were separated because listeners have different understandings of their meaning. It was necessary to clarify the meaning of the statement and possibly formulate it differently. The authors of the study believe that the unified nature of communication as such has been proven.

(2). Differences in the form of teaching are not fundamental under conditions when students feel care, respect from the teacher, friendly attitude, etc. However, in our opinion, it is important to establish, at the beginning of training, live contact with students in contact learning. This will help to more consistently form an integral structure of pedagogical communication and create prerequisites for the professional growth of students.

(3). With distant learning, it is important to fill the study time with a sufficient number of exercises, creative tasks, the implementation of which does not require much time, so that students learn most of the essential concepts when communicating with the teacher. This, in turn, will remove the problem of formal answers when performing independent assignments.

ADHERENCE TO ETHICAL STANDARDS

Ethics Declarations. Participation in the research (for the sample group) was done on a voluntary basis. Participants were informed about the research and were asked to sign a voluntary consent form. All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards. The study was approved by the University of Latvia.

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Conflict of Interest. Authors have no conflict of interest.

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References

- Aleksandrovich, P.I. (2012). Pedagogicheskaja kultura prepodavatelya vuza [Pedagogical Culture of a University Teacher]. *Trudi BGTU – Publications BGTU*, 5, 77–79. URL: <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=25141661> [in Russian].
- Bolshoi psihologicheskij slovar* [Great Psychological Dictionary]. (2008). In V.P. Zinchenko, & B.G. Meshcheryakov (Eds.). URL: <https://obuchalka.org/20190807112181/bolshoi-psihologicheskii-slovar-zinchenko-v-p-mescheryakov-b-g-2008.html> [in Russian].
- Duchnovskij, S.V. (2013). *Garmoniya i dizgarmoniya mezhlichnostnih otnoshenij subjektov obrazovatel'nogo processa* [Harmoni and Disharmony of Interpersonal Relation of Subjects of the Educational Process]. Yekaterinburg. URL: <https://www.dissercat.com/content/garmoniya-i-disgarmoniya-mezhlichnostnykh-otnoshenii-subektov-obrazovatel'nogo-protsesssa> [in Russian].
- Guzhva, I.V. (2011). *Psichologicheskije osobennosti pedagogicheskogo obshchenia prepodavatel-student v sovremennom vuze* [Psychological Features of Pedagogical Communication of Teacher-student in a Modern University]. Bryansk. URL: <http://nauka-pedagogika.com/psihologiya-19-00-07/dissertaciya-psihologicheskije-osobennosti-pedagogicheskogo-obscheniya-prepodavatel-student-v-sovremennom-vuze> [in Russian].
- Guzhva, I.V., & Pobokin, P.A. (2020). Obraz prepodavatelya v predstavlenii sovremennich studentov v usloviyach uchebno-vospitatelnogo processa [The Image of a Teacher in the View of Modern Students in the Context of an Educational Process]. *Yaroslavskij pedagogicheskij vestnik – Yaroslavl Pedagogical Bulletin*, 6(117), 139–145. <https://doi.org/10.20323/1813-145X-2020-6-117-139-145> [in Russian].
- Kan-Kalic, V.A. (1987). *Uchitelju o pedagogicheskom obshchenii: Kniga dlya uchitelja* [To the Teacher about Pedagogical Communication. A book for teachers]. Moscow: Prosveshchenie (Education) [in Russian].
- Shakirov, R.R. (2009). Rolj pedagogicheskogo obshchenija v uchebnoj [The Role of Pedagogical Communication in Educational Activities]. *Kazanskij pedagogicheskij zhurnal – Kazan Pedagogical Journal*, 2, 19–22. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rolj-pedagogicheskogo-obscheniya-v-uchebnoj-deyatelnosti/viewer> [in Russian].

АНОТАЦІЯ

Вступ. Актуальність теми визначається практикою дистанційного навчання та необхідністю вдосконалення підходів до організації та змісту занять зі студентами педагогічних спеціальностей. Проблеми навчання з використанням інформаційних технологій розроблялися давно, але раніше вони стосувалися додаткової та інших видів освіти, де здобувачі освіти в основному володіли професійними навичками. У даному дослідженні мова йде про студентів, які тільки починають навчання і коли якість педагогічного спілкування впливає не тільки на засвоєння навчального матеріалу, а й формує вміння та стиль діяльності в освітньому процесі самих студентів. Оскільки частина занять проходила в контактному режимі, важливо було з'ясувати, як студенти оцінюють заняття в різних форматах, зокрема, структуру спілкування та навички, необхідні для самостійної роботи.

Мета. Метою дослідження є порівняння та оцінка окремих аспектів спілкування в очному та дистанційному навчанні.

Методи дослідження. Методами дослідження було опитування та анкетування 116 та 84 студентів першого курсу педагогічних спеціальностей Латвійського університету у 2020–2021 рр.

Результати. На першому етапі на основі анкетування було визначено критерії успішності педагогічного спілкування викладача та студентів у процесі навчання. На другому етапі було проведено анкетування студентів з метою оцінки професійних якостей викладача та студента, які визначають оптимальне педагогічне спілкування.

Висновки. Отримані результати показали високий рівень оцінок професійних якостей викладача та задоволеності рівнем педагогічного спілкування самими студентами, а також мінімальну різницю в оцінках на контактних і дистанційних заняттях. Це означає, що характер спілкування єдиний і включає повагу до студентів, доброзичливе ставлення до них, захоплення роботою, повагу до самостійності один одного та вимогливість, що дозволяє кожному інтелектуально розвиватися, оволодівати професійними навичками та індивідуальними засобами навчання, враховуючи індивідуальні якості здобувачів освіти.

Ключові слова: педагогічне спілкування, структура педагогічного спілкування, професійна майстерність викладача.

